

THE ROLE OF LAW ENFORCEMENT AUTHORITIES IN THE FIGHT AGAINST EXTREMISM AND IDIOLOGY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12192386>

Abstract. *The main tasks and cooperation of representatives of each field in connection with terrorism and religious extremism, which is one of the areas of activity, are discussed.*

Keywords: *fanaticism, terrorism and extremism, internal affairs bodies, the main activity of a number of services, patriotism.*

Today, combating the scourge of fanaticism, terrorism and extremism is defined as the main activity of a number of services of internal affairs bodies.

The main tasks and cooperation of representatives of each field related to terrorism and religious extremism, which is one of the areas of activity, are defined in the relevant normative legal documents of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. Internal affairs bodies cooperate with law enforcement agencies in order to effectively organize activities related to terrorism and religious extremism and to achieve positive results in this direction. In carrying out activities on terrorism and religious extremism, it is of particular importance to organize cooperation of internal affairs bodies, first of all, with sectoral services, and this cooperation is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, laws of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, law enforcement it is organized based on the requirements of the regulatory legal documents of the regulatory bodies.

If we pay attention to the fight against terrorism, we see that international cooperation is implemented in several directions. Criminal acts defined as dangerous and illegal for the society of states are recognized as terrorist acts, regardless of who and where they are committed. Because this risk affects the interests of not one, but two or more countries, that is, if such actions are committed on the territory of foreign countries, the citizens of other countries are also becoming their victims.

In order to effectively ensure large-scale cooperation in the fight against terrorism and extremism, it is necessary to organize, coordinate and manage this cooperation.

After all, as President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "Currently, in the world, opposition and conflicts between different forces are increasing, and there is a fierce struggle for resources. There are new threats to peace and security in our region" [1, p.371].

As defined in the normative legal documents, organization, coordination and management of cooperation between the sectoral services of internal affairs bodies at the district and city level, as well as their cooperation with the public, is carried out by the following persons:

a) cooperation management - by the head of the district, city internal affairs department (department) and his deputies;

b) coordination of cooperation - by the head of the department (division) of the department (department) of the district, city internal affairs department (department) of the Combating Terrorism and Extremism (T and EQK);

v) organization of cooperation - by senior operational representatives of T and EQK department.

The head of the internal affairs department (department) is the highest person responsible for managing large-scale cooperation in T and EQK at the district, city level.

Management of cooperation on the basis of T and EQK is the activity of issuing executive orders by authorized state bodies and officials on the organizational-methodical, legal, material and technical provision of cooperation between the employees of the internal affairs bodies and the public on the basis of T and EQK is considered

It should be noted that the boundaries of the territory served by T and EQK and the operative (senior) representatives serving in them are determined by the head of the city and district IIB in agreement with the mayors of the said city or district on the scale of neighborhood areas.

The monthly work plan drawn up by immediate (senior) representatives is approved by the head of the city, district IIB or his first deputy.

The cooperative activities of T and EQK are discussed at monthly, quarterly, semi-annual and year-end meetings in the presence of the head of the city, district IIB or one of his deputies. Specific measures will be determined in order to eliminate identified deficiencies and improve the efficiency of work in this regard in the future.

In these meetings, a quick (senior) representative will provide information about the shortcomings made in cooperation with the work on the fight against and prevention of terrorism-related crimes, as well as about the employees who regularly violated service discipline during the cooperation, deviated from the set routes and achieved low performance, and came to help. and, in necessary cases, makes reasonable proposals for disciplinary punishment and, if necessary, dismissal from the positions held by employees who grossly violated service discipline during cooperation.

An important aspect of the head of the district, city internal affairs department (management) in managing the activities of T and EQK and the large-scale cooperation based on them is the organizational-methodical and material-technical work aimed at the effective organization and improvement of this activity or cooperation, and the elimination of identified problems and shortcomings. makes management decisions and supervises their implementation. This is an integral part of managing the activities of T and EQK and the large-scale cooperation based on them - it serves to provide legal support.

In addition, the reception and transfer of the service area by the employee appointed to the position of the operational (senior) representative of T and EQK is carried out with the direct participation of the head of the city, district internal affairs office, his first deputy or the head of the T and EQK department.

The head of the district, city internal affairs department (management) in most cases, on the basis of T and EQK, manages the mutual cooperation of the employees of the sectorial services of the internal affairs bodies, as well as their cooperation with the public through his deputies.

In the system of district and city internal affairs bodies, implementation of rapid-search measures based on T and EQK, detection of committed crimes, identification and capture of wanted persons, fight against terrorism and religious extremism, in particular, implementation of rapid measures for this purpose. Large-scale cooperation is managed by the first deputy head of the department (department) of internal affairs.

Powers of state bodies and non-governmental organizations. According to the current regulatory legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the main responsibility for managing cooperation based on T and EQK is assigned to the deputy head of the district, city internal affairs department (administration), who heads the preventive service.

It is necessary to use the capabilities of agencies working in different directions to solve the crime of terrorism and extremism. Therefore, in this case, there is a need to ensure close cooperation between some units. One of the most important issues to be solved by the chief as he organizes cooperation in solving crimes of terrorism and extremism is the organization of a system of mutual information exchange. It represents an existing specific information center (bank) that serves as a unique dispatching point for the distribution of information as needed and at the request of cooperating services and units. The task is to ensure familiarization of services and departments with the types of information in the data bank: to constantly fill the information set with new information; according to the requests of interested services, it is to provide the necessary information for them in a timely manner. For this purpose, to determine the procedures for sending and receiving relevant information from duty units to services and divisions, to ensure the development of appropriate forms of documents (requests, information carriers); it is necessary to ensure timely changes to existing documents (model plans, calculations, etc.). The organization of such a system of mutual information exchange allows to ensure the timely exchange of necessary information with the cooperating service, makes it easier to solve the crime and search for the criminal.

The chief's organization of solving crimes by working on hot leads does not end there. He takes personal responsibility for all stages of ensuring this field of work, that is, up to sending the criminal case to court. If it is not possible to solve the crime in the first days after the commission of the crime, the chief should ensure that comprehensive measures are taken for each possible incident, critically evaluate the results of the previously developed plans, determine and organize the implementation of additional investigation and rapid search measures. ; should regularly monitor their implementation.

In particular, the chief's activity in organizing the investigation of crimes at the next stages is represented by the time factor. The situation is also complicated by the fact that the employees work on solving newly committed crimes. It should be noted that the activity of the units is evaluated based on the number of crimes registered in previous years. Despite the fact that in statistical reports a separate line (graph) has been allocated to the indicators of the detection of crimes over the past years, in practice this is not actually taken into account and does not affect the overall assessment of the work of internal affairs agencies. In such conditions, it is natural that the activity of the employees in solving crimes will decrease, they will not be solved, and the number of such crimes will increase.

At this stage of solving the crimes of terrorism and extremism, the head should ensure the succession of the previous measures and organizational forms of cooperation in the organization of cooperation between services and units. The main efforts of the participants of cooperation

should be focused on the search for information about the crime being committed (committed) and the circumstances of the persons involved in it. The initiative to implement this or that measure must come from the investigator conducting the criminal case. This does not mean that the head himself does not propose this initiative.

Cooperation does not end if the person who committed the crime is identified. In this context, the tasks of the participants of the cooperation will be to gain comprehensiveness, to fully identify all the circumstances defining the subject of proof in the criminal case, to identify and expose all the participants of the crime, to prove all aspects of their criminal activity.

Cooperation should continue until the investigation is completed. It is necessary to manage the intensity of cooperative investigative efforts and search and rescue measures, taking into account the achieved results. After the participants of the cooperation take drastic measures to solve the crime, a decision is made to stop the cooperation according to the proposal of the head of the investigative-operational group.

During the organization of cooperation in solving crimes, the efforts of the participants of joint activities are to collect, systematize and collect information on unsolved criminal cases, establish contact with the operatives of the JIB and use their capabilities, use public representatives, use the capabilities of the mass media and focused on the implementation of complex measures on etc. For this purpose, a special operative group is formed and it is the main organizational link for solving such crimes.

The stability of the composition of such groups, the uniformity of the work performed by them, the planning of the activities of each member of the group, constant control over their activities, practical and methodical support should be ensured.

The cooperation with the operational services of the special operational-investigative group of the JIB, the investigative detention center (TH), the temporary storage room (VSX), and the rehabilitation centers will give positive results. It is also important to ensure the study of other information of interest in criminal cases in the archive on similar crimes.

Analysis of crime, unsolved crimes (type of crimes, place and method of their commission, object of criminal aggression, methods of concealment of crime, etc.) plays an important role in ensuring cooperation of members of the special specialized operative-investigative team.

Investigations are an integral part of the fight against crime. Among the unsearched criminals, dangerous criminals occupy a significant place, and it should be noted that there are serious shortcomings in the activities in this direction. One of the reasons for such situations is the poor organization of local organizations. City and district leaders of internal affairs agencies pay little attention to the search for criminals, do not thoroughly study the reasons for bad searches, do not ensure the full use of forces and means in the search for criminals, and their cooperation at the required level.

All services and units must be involved in the search for a hidden criminal. The organization of these works is entrusted to the heads of cities and districts. It is they who must ensure the wide use of the powers and means of these bodies. They are responsible for organizing the cooperation of these forces, as well as cooperation with certain internal affairs agencies (with the approval of senior leaders).

The main volume of search operations is carried out by T and EQK divisions. Therefore, when organizing cooperation, they are usually appointed to be responsible for the implementation of one or another search activity in cooperation.

Heads of cities and districts in the organization of cooperation should ensure effective use of the opportunities of each of the cooperating parties in search in various forms and methods of work, provide them with practical assistance, carry out constant control over the implementation of search measures, study best practices in search and should spread.

The choice of the forms of organization of such cooperation should be made taking into account the characteristics of the crime committed by the wanted person, circumstances of his person's escape, opportunities of cooperation participants. In any case, the attention and efforts of the participants of cooperation: identifying and studying the lifestyle and behavior of the wanted person, his relatives and acquaintances, and the persons with whom he had a relationship or who helped him to hide; in the places where it is likely to appear, to register the persons coming and going to this address, to carry out continuous operational surveillance in order to recognize the wanted person based on his appearance, photo or behavioral signs; conducting secret or disguised inspections of his former residence and the residences of his relatives and other close people; conducting surveillance in places where the wanted person is likely to appear; to influence relatives and acquaintances of the wanted person in order to convince him to bear his guilt; checking existing accounts etc.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Terrorism" (this law was amended on April 30, 2004 and with its additions that came into force on July 6, 2004).

Article 6. Assistance to the state bodies implementing the fight against terrorism.

State management bodies, local government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, public associations, enterprises, institutions and organizations, officials, as well as citizens assist and provide necessary assistance to state bodies implementing the fight against terrorism.

Article 7. International cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the fight against terrorism.

Cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with foreign countries, their law enforcement agencies, special services and international organizations in the field of combating terrorism is carried out in accordance with the international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Persons guilty of violations of the laws on the fight against terrorism shall be held responsible in accordance with the established procedure.

Article 8. State bodies for the fight against terrorism.

The state bodies implementing the fight against terrorism are as follows:

- State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- State security service of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Department of Combating Economic Crimes under the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall coordinate the activities of the state bodies involved in the fight against terrorism and ensure that they work together to prevent, detect, and limit terrorist activities and minimize their consequences.

Positive influence of creative ideas and ideologies in the life of society. The power that preserves humanity from all kinds of destruction is goodness. Virtue is the cornerstone of the emergence, formation and development of creative ideas and ideologies. Not everyone is born brave or cowardly, generous or stingy, honest or thieving, hardworking or lazy, friend or enemy, rich or poor, loyal or treacherous, loyal or unfaithful. He is born as an ordinary human child from his mother. Positive or negative characteristics and qualities of a person are formed and developed during his life as a result of the upbringing he received in the family, school, neighborhood, workplace, and the influence of the spiritual and moral environment in society.

Since the beginning of humanity, two forces - goodness and evil - have been constantly fighting each other in its spiritual body. Goodness encourages people to live peacefully, and evil encourages them to do evil deeds. It is not surprising that the good - constructive ideas and ideologies, and the evil - destructive, destructive ideas and ideologies in the ways of this struggle, which has been going on for centuries, have been born. After all, the history of humanity consists not only of the history of wars and riots between people and nations on the battlefields, but also of the history of struggles between ideas.

The historical forms and content of ideas and ideologies have always been determined by the dialectic of the struggle between good and evil, creativity and destruction, that is, in contrast to the ideologies of invasion, getting rich at the expense of others, aggression, and fanaticism, the ideas of freedom, independence and justice have been constantly emerging. , has become the victorious flag of nations.

Creative ideas that glorify man and society, increase his energy and potential, and mobilize him to do useful things for his people, the Motherland, and the whole of humanity, embody noble goals such as work, development, friendship, freedom, independence, peace, justice, and honesty. is said to the idea.

Features of the manifestation of creative ideas:

- encourages the people to work together towards a noble goal, leads to progress;
- expresses the hopes and goals of every nation, glorifies free life and a fair system;
- increases human dignity in every way, increases the well-being of the people;
- a moral criterion that determines the extent to which each person fulfills his duty to society, country, nation, himself and his family;
- as an ideological way of thinking, finds solutions to problems arising in society;
- correctly analyzes events, evaluates them, makes logical conclusions.

Creative ideas are distinguished by their noble goals of making the country prosperous and people's lives prosperous. They have been living as the noblest ideals of the life of the society since the time when mankind reached civilization. The meaning of these eternal ideas is also reflected in the words of our President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Our nation is historically capable of great deeds." Such creativity has been inherited by our people from their ancestors.

The idea of national statehood and its positive impact on the development of nations can be clearly seen in the case of the new Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan's policy of international cooperation, regional peace, inter-ethnic harmony serves as a basis for the rule of stability.

Scientific discoveries also greatly influence the development of ideology. Advances in modern science, such as cosmonautics, cybernetics, nanotechnology, great discoveries such as determining the genetic map of a person, are dramatically changing people's imagination.

At the same time, high scientific and technical progress, processes of globalization, on the one hand, increase confidence in the possibilities of human intelligence and the future, on the other hand, they also cause universal problems such as the tragedies of Hiroshima, Nagasaki, Chernobyl, weapons of mass destruction, ecological disasters, spiritual decline. .

Therefore, the society needs a healthy idea and a healthy ideology for the rational use of scientific and cultural achievements.

If philosophy and ideology do not reflect the principles of humanism and development, the need for progress in the destiny of the people, on the contrary, if it rejects these aspirations, in essence, contradicts them, it causes the decline of society.

One of these ideologies is the ideology of the former communist regime, which seized power by force of arms. This ideology, which prevailed in the territory of a huge kingdom and a socialist camp, which occupied one sixth of the world, fell into decline due to its inhuman and non-national essence and authoritarian nature.

The realities of life show that sometimes destructive ideas can poison the public mind with their false charm, deception and trickery and take a dominant position in society. For example, the victory of fascism in Italy and Germany in the 30s of the 20th century brought immense hardship not only to the Italian and German people, but also to millions of people around the world. However, these ideas began to appear in these countries from the beginning of the century. For example, in Italy, since 1910, the magazine "National Idea" began to be published, in which aggressive nationalism was promoted. The rise of Nazism to power in Germany in the early 1930s led to the outbreak of World War II. Unfortunately, because it was not abolished in its time, it became a temporary dominant idea and caused millions of victims.

Today, progressive and humanist forces around the world are working together to prevent such tragic and unpleasant situations from happening again. In the words of Islam Karimov, since time immemorial, mankind has been struggling with idea against idea, thought against thought, and enlightenment against ignorance - this is an unchanging law of history.

The negative impact of destructive ideas and ideologies on the life of society. As long as people and society exist, tyranny and violence, arrogance and ignorance, which are contrary to good ideas, try to manifest in new forms. But they cannot stop people from striving towards higher goals based on the ideas of justice, peace and brotherhood, development and prosperity.

Dissatisfaction of people with reality: envy, anger, impatience, intolerance, panic, fear, invisibility, betrayal, etc. lead them to evil behavior: slander, gossip, lying, espionage, violence, threats, aggression. came In the world, the mechanisms of implementation of destructive ideas and ideologies are being developed and launched across ideological fields by individuals, public organizations, and even states who support these actions.

Ensuring legality, rights and freedoms of citizens and their legitimate interests in the fight against terrorism and extremism; constant rapid readiness; targeted and effective implementation of the events; effective and comprehensive conduct of overt and undercover rapid-search forces, tools and activities; is carried out in strict compliance with the principles of close cooperation with other ministries, departments, enterprises, institutions, organizations and the public.

Based on our national mentality, even if there is only one boy in the family and the rest are girls, these young men are given the privilege of serving in the area where their parents live, have a positive recommendation, and are given one rank higher than officers who have completed at least two years of service in the military rank given because there are no vacant positions.

Privileges such as the granting of a standing military rank, the granting of additional 5, 10, 15 days of leave to the next vacation of military personnel according to the calendar of years of service were created.

Strong social protection, in turn, creates the ground for our officers and soldiers to serve with dedication, devotion to duty, and to improve their professional training. As a result of the complex measures - measures taken, the approach of the defenders of the Motherland to military service has fundamentally changed, responsibility and discipline have been strengthened in the military units, and the feeling of pride and pride in the Motherland has increased in the hearts of all military personnel.

As stated by the President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy" is an important direction.

The essence of the large-scale reforms being implemented under the leadership of the President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev calls for people to understand and feel the human factor in life and their internal capabilities more deeply, and not to shy away from work.

The spiritual and physical development of citizens, especially the youth of the country, with the feeling of high civic responsibility through the idea of national development, peace and welfare of the people, understanding, learning and understanding, as well as the feeling of direct commitment to the society are our great goals. will be a solid foundation for its implementation.

Not only military, but also social-political, spiritual-educational and trade-economic issues are gaining importance in the context of the wide-scale reforms implemented in the new Uzbekistan society. That's why President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, relying on the principle of peace, stability and humanity in the increasing position of Uzbekistan in the world community, put the life, dreams, pains and dreams of every person living in our country in the center of our attention and increasing the efficiency of tasks in this regard as the most important issue on the agenda. is putting

Today's world is experiencing information attacks. For this reason, analytical assimilation of information is becoming one of the most urgent issues in the thinking of not only the population but also military personnel. Therefore, in accordance with the decrees and decisions of the President, Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the instructions of the Minister of Defense, Lieutenant General Bahadir Kurbanov, and the instructions of the head of the Academy, Colonel Bobur Shayakubov, the interest, mood, and social status of all personnel and social groups cadet studying at our Academy based on the need to study and acquire the skills to analyze the influence of the destructive ideas of extremists active in the media world with scientific observation, that is, to strengthen the spirit of patriotism and to listeners, sergeants who are taking qualification classes, professors regularly teach "Moral and educational foundations of the fight against fanaticism and extremism", "Combat and moral-spiritual support", "Military psychology", " In addition to such subjects as "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan", in addition, "Spiritual - educational preparation" classes are conducted from an educational and ideological point of view. The goal is to educate our military, which is the pillar of peace and stability in today's global world, in the spirit of strong will and moral-educational trust in all aspects".

Ensuring security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in our country was considered the priority of our state policy. Representatives of more than 130 nationalities and

peoples living in our country have united in 138 national and cultural centers and live peacefully as children of a big family under the slogan "Uzbekistan is our common home". At the root of this is a great humanitarian policy. In accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2017, the committee "International relations and friendly relations with foreign countries" was established. The main goal of this is to consistently continue the state policy aimed at ensuring inter-ethnic harmony and tolerance in our society.

We must always be alert and vigilant in the present time, when the process of globalization has intensified in the world, competition and mutual contradictions are intensifying on a global scale, threats such as radicalism, terrorism, extremism, proselytism and "mass culture" are expanding.

After all, as stated by the President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Nowadays in the world, opposition and conflicts between different forces are increasing, fierce struggle for resources is going on. There are new threats to peace and security in our region."

Life itself requires us to further increase our mobilization through the ideas of "Protect your own home", "Protect your own child". We need to educate our young men and women in the spirit of patriotism, ensuring the integrity of the country's borders and strengthening the combat potential of our Armed Forces.

Currently, our Armed Forces have improved significantly in terms of organization and structure. The mobility of structures, fighting ability, and physical and moral training of the military have increased. Units and units are equipped with modern weapons and combat equipment. Today, in a situation where many countries of the world are facing serious problems of various forms, during the past thirty-two years of independence in our country, especially in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, as a result of the reforms consistently implemented by our respected President in all fields, the life of our people is improving day by day. is keeping up with the times. At this point, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in his speech at the 78th session of the UN General Assembly on September 19, 2023: "Development of human capital and education of a creative young generation is one of the strategic tasks that Uzbekistan has set before itself. We believe that quality education, open to all, is the most effective factor in eradicating poverty, improving people's well-being, and achieving sustainable economic growth. The essence of this is to invite a person to a deeper understanding of his human factor in life and his inner potential. Based on this, in accordance with the principle of social policy, in addition to the monthly salaries of scientific potential professors - teachers engaged in pedagogic activities at the Academy, up to 200% bonus is given.

That's why the President, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, while paying close attention to the defense sector as well as all fronts, there will be such problems that will always remain relevant. Among them there are issues related to the spiritual and moral improvement of a person. In fact, in the concept of increasing the effectiveness of moral and educational work in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the moral level and intellectual potential of military personnel, instilling a sense of responsibility for the protection of state security, pride in our national army, pays special attention to the fact that tasks such as forming a conscious attitude and an active life position in relation to the processes of globalization taking place in the world and around us are defined.

Today, high demands are placed on the moral and ethical qualities of all categories of military personnel, and special attention is paid to strengthening the ideological and physical training of personnel, improving their combat skills, and strengthening discipline. As the intellectual and mental stress of the service increases, the need for further development of the officer's discipline remains on the agenda. After all, discipline is the main strength of the army.

Ensuring the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work" dated May 3, 2019 No. According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1059 of December 31, 2019, the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" was adopted. According to this concept, effective implementation of the tasks related to the education of the population, especially the youth, provided for in the Action Strategy on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, providing them with the most necessary basic competencies for a peaceful life, spiritual development of scientifically based indicators for the assessment of upbringing, based on the principles of continuity and coherence in the upbringing process, first of all, the correct organization of the mother's pregnancy period, and the determination of the main directions for the spiritual upbringing of babies and children were shown. Now, the duration of this process is included in the seven priorities of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.

Discipline is primarily a concept related to activity and behavior. Discipline is a set of specific requirements for people's behavior that meet social norms established in society. It reflects, firstly, the specific demands of society on individuals and communities, and secondly, the social assessment of the conformity of human behavior to the interests of society, its legitimacy and internal culture. Discipline is a necessary remedy against various forms and degrees of disorder.

The following types of discipline are distinguished according to the spheres of action: state discipline, labor discipline, military discipline, contract-based discipline, financial discipline, technological discipline. These are:

- State discipline - a type of discipline related to the fulfillment of requirements imposed on civil servants;
- labor discipline - a form of social relations that leads its participants to mandatory obedience to certain established rules during the labor process. It is governed by the norms of labor law;
- discipline based on the contract - compliance of the subjects with the obligations and legal relations specified in the contract;
- financial discipline - compliance of subjects with budget, tax and other financial legal instructions;
- technological discipline - compliance of subjects with technological instructions in the production process;
- military discipline - is explained by the rules of compliance of military personnel with established laws, regulations, and orders.

So, thanks to the large-scale work in the military field, strict discipline, spiritual and educational thinking will rise.

"At the moment, we all see how fierce the competition is on the world scale. We can adequately respond to this fierce competition only by widely introducing the achievements of modern science, high technologies and innovation."

On June 29, 2023, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to increase the effectiveness of education of young people in the military-patriotic spirit" was adopted.

Based on this decision, a 7-chapter concept on educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism was adopted in 2023-2027, and implementation of the decision and concept was determined in 14 territorial units. It is intended to unite young people on the basis of the conceptual idea "Motherland is great, duty is sacred".

The strength of our army depends on the unity and solidarity of the military personnel and our entire society. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that as long as this source of spiritual power exists, no evil force can interfere with the independence of Uzbekistan, our peaceful and peaceful life, or turn us back from the path of democratic changes.

As a result of fundamental reforms carried out in recent years, our national army has become a powerful, quick and effective force capable of striking any danger.

Our Armed Forces have established close partnerships with their counterparts in Central Asian countries, and a number of joint training exercises have been held. Visits of high-level military delegations were organized, experience was exchanged in operational and combat training. Such cooperation is becoming an important factor in ensuring regional security and stability, peace and tranquility in our common home called Central Asia.

The system of continuous military education organized on the basis of world standards is developing consistently. Currently, the newly formed Military Institute of Information - Communication Technologies and Communications has its proper place.

The Faculty of Military Security and State Defense was established at the Academy of Armed Forces, which prepares officers who will serve in the operational and strategic link of management.

Today, our military personnel are proving that they are not inferior to the military personnel of the armies of the world's leading countries in terms of their level of professional training. At international military training competitions, inter-army and sports competitions, representatives of Uzbekistan demonstrate their skills, mental strength, will to victory, and clearly show that they are the worthy successors of our great ancestors.

Tasks for the further development of the defense-industrial complex capable of supplying our national army with weapons and other necessary means are being solved step by step.

A clear example of this is the modernization and technical re-equipment of the Chirchik aviation repair plant and the enterprise that produces combat ammunition - drugs, and the reorganized scientific and technical potential in them is becoming the basis for the formation of scientific and production clusters in these industries.

In the near future, the ongoing work on the formation of a full-fledged defense sector of our country will not only provide the national army with weapons and equipment, but also create additional jobs, as well as diversify the country's economy.

Military settlements have acquired a modern appearance, outsourcing system has been introduced in the field of material supply services. Over the past years, more than 300 multi-story buildings have been built to provide comfortable and cozy apartments for the families of more

than 15,000 military personnel, about 1,000 new jobs have been created for women of military personnel, and 2,400 military pensioners have been employed.

Our army actively engaged in educating the growing young generation in the spirit of patriotism and love for the motherland, respect for our national values and traditions, and deep knowledge of our glorious history. Organizations such as "Vatanparvar" and "Veterans", as well as the Public Council under the Ministry of Defense, continue to work together to strengthen the education of young people in the military-patriotic spirit and to form an active civil position in them.

In conclusion, the sense of patriotism is strengthened by understanding, feeling and understanding the military sphere. For example, based on the above legal, social, spiritual-educational and political factors, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 23, 2022 "On measures - measures to fundamentally improve the activities of the Academy of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" "and the implementation of the decisions of September 8, 2022 "On additional measures to increase the moral and spiritual training and fighting spirit of military personnel" is an important strategic factor for the country's development. serves.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (F-79) dated December 14, 2023 "On preparations and measures to celebrate the 32nd anniversary of the establishment of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Day of Defenders of the Fatherland" (F-79) and the army - one flesh and one soul!" in order to convey the principle to the general public, it was decided to organize spiritual, educational and cultural promotion events in all regions of our Republic. Based on this, family members of servicemen and employees who died in the defense of the Motherland and national peace, servicemen who became disabled while performing their duty, participants of the Second World War who need attention and support and veterans, as well as charity events related to providing material and moral support to Armed Forces veterans are canceled.

There are certain achievements in the activities of the military-administrative sectors, which have become a reliable bridge between the people and the army. Since the establishment of these sectors, large-scale work on modernization of military infrastructures and solving accumulated social problems has been carried out under the slogan "The people and the army are one and the same soul". 2024 is the "Year of supporting youth and business" in Uzbekistan, based on the programmatic idea "From national revival to national growth", educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to the motherland, forming initiative, self-sacrifice, moral qualities and patriotism in them is the most important. is one of the important tasks. . So, today, under the leadership of the President, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, the professional army has become the main force of our nation based on the principle of "People and army - one body and one soul". As a result, our country is strengthening its position in the world axis, as a result of the large-scale reforms being carried out in the new Uzbekistan.

Therefore, according to the seven priority directions defined in the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the state program "Year of attention to people and quality education", "Prosperous village", "Prosperous neighborhood", "Every family is an entrepreneur", "Youth is our future", Based on the meaning and content of reforms carried out within the framework of important programs and plans such as "Five positive initiatives", the main ideological principles of this decree put the human factor in a high position.

We are convinced that the policy of Uzbekistan, which is on the path of developing a legal democratic state and a fair civil society based on the free market economy under the leadership of our President, focuses on the development of the society. The activities of public organizations, political institutions and mass media are synchronized with today's processes in the implementation of comprehensive reforms aimed at the liberalization of state administration, improvement of the state and society. The fact that the state and its policies are focused only on the benefit of the people, on ensuring the peace and stable life of the country's citizens is reflected in the adopted laws, presidential decrees and decisions, and is implemented in life. Along with determining the material and cultural image of the society, this has a positive effect on the spiritual and educational, moral thinking and worldview of the citizens of the country. That is why it creates an opportunity to harmonize the relations between the state and the citizens, the authorities and the population based on justice. Under the leadership of our head of state, our people live peacefully, positive economic changes are taking place step by step in our country. New opportunities are being opened for entrepreneurial, knowledgeable, hardworking people.

The principle that the people should serve our people and not the state agencies is being widely applied in life. Life itself shows the necessity of achieving justice in the legal system, ensuring citizens' confidence in the future, and raising the human factor by making an impartial assessment of the activities of state bodies.

Ensuring the viability and enforcement of adopted laws should become a priority in society. Now, in the state and non-state sector, as well as in the entire production, there is a need for specialist employees, employees who quickly get involved in economic reforms, and personnel who meet the requirements of market relations and the requirements of modern world technology. Therefore, it is an important task to move from general production to production based on advanced technologies, to increase the volume of export of products, and to train employees who think in a new way in today's market conditions.

Today, in a situation where many countries of the world are facing serious problems of various forms, the life of our people is improving day by day as a result of the reforms carried out consistently in all fields by our honorable President during the past thirty-two years of independence, especially in the conditions of New Uzbekistan. At this point, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in his speech at the 78th session of the UN General Assembly on September 19, 2023: "Development of human capital and education of the creative young generation is one of the strategic tasks that Uzbekistan has set before itself. We consider open and high-quality education for everyone to be the most effective factor for eradicating poverty, improving people's well-being and achieving sustainable economic growth" [2, p.1-2.], he noted. The essence of this is to invite a person to a deeper understanding of his human factor in life and his inner potential. Therefore, we will solve the above-mentioned problems by educating young people with knowledge.

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